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EDITORS

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Adela Krivohlavek

Jasna Bošnjir

Sandra Šikić

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4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality ONE HEALTH

November 9th-12th, 2022 | Dubrovnik, Croatia

4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality “One Health”

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Dear colleagues, dear friends,

It is my great honour and pleasure to invite you on behalf of the Organising and Scientific Committee to participate in the 4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality under the slogan “One Health”, which will be held in Dubrovnik, from 9 to 12 November 2022.

The International Congress on Food Safety and Quality will again be held under the auspices of the competent authorities and institutions and is organised by the Andrija Štampar Teaching Institute of Public Health, the Croatian Metrology Society, and the Southeast European Food Quality and Safety Control Network (SEEN-FSQC). The co-organisers are the Faculty of Agriculture and the Faculty of Food Technology and Biotechnology, the University of Zagreb, the Institute for Health and Food Safety Zenica, and the Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, in cooperation with other eminent institutions from the country and abroad.

Thanks to the extremely important topics and the esteemed experts who shared their knowledge and experiences with us at the first three Congresses on Food Safety and Quality, we were all happy to see

truly great interest: the Congresses New Achievements and Future Challenges in 2017, Food Life Cycle in 2018, and Food, Health and Climate Change in 2020 were attended by nearly 1,000 participants, while numerous guest speakers from the country and the world presented their colourful presentations in the form of exceptional plenary lectures, excellent oral presentations, satellite symposia, workshops, and posters. On the wings of these successes, our goal is to organise an even more significant, distinctive, and educational 4th International Congress on Food Safety and Quality.

We will present the significant experiences of domestic and foreign experts in the field of food counterfeiting, protection of the origin and geographical origin of food, and new, exact analytical achievements in this field.

Food safety and quality, determination of food origin and geographical origin, adulteration of food and its impact on consumer health, as well as the impact of climate change on farming and quality are all topics of crucial significance and impose a shared responsibility on all stakeholders in the food production chain. These are primarily countries, producers, distributors, consumers, but also the media, which are responsible for accurately reporting current topics to the public, including this very relevant issue.

Given that our common task is not only to protect, but also to improve the health of each of our residents, by organising the 4th International Congress “One Health” we also want to continue to raise awareness of this important topic in the profession.

Thank you for your response.

Sincerely,
Prof Branko Kolarić, MD, PhD
Congress President

Evaluation of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons in fermented dried sausages from the Serbian market

J. Djinovic-Stojanovic*, S. Jankovic, V. Djordjevic, D. Nikolic-Perovic, D. Vranic, I. Brankovic-Lazic, and N. Borjan

Institute of Meat Hygiene and Technology, Belgrade, Serbia

Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) are compounds that widely geographically distributed and remain in the environment for a long time. Meat and meat products may be contaminated by PAHs through the process of food smoking. This study provides original analytical data on the levels of benzo[a]pyrene and sum of PAH4 compounds [benzo[a]pyrene (BaP), benzo[a]anthracene (BaA), benzo[b]fluoranthene (BbF), and chrysene (CHR)] in different types of fermented dried sausages commonly consumed in Serbia. A total of 228 fermented dried sausages, collected from 2020 to 2021, were classified in 4 groups (kulen, cajna, sremska, and budimska sausage). Homogenized samples were extracted by acetonitrile. The purification procedure of the extract was based on the Quick Easy Cheap Effective Rugged and Safe (QuEChERS) approach. Levels of estimated PAH compounds were determined by gas chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (GC-MS/MS). The following ranges were found ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$): kulen (n=56): BaP <0.2–0.5, PAH4 <0.2–2.5; cajna (n=103): BaP <0.2–1.0, PAH4 <0.2–8.6; sremska (n=37): BaP <0.2–0.4, PAH4 <0.2–3.4; budimska (n=32): BaP <0.2–0.3, PAH4 <0.2–1.4. The maximum residue limits (MRL) for BaP and sum of PAH4 compounds, which were defined both by the legislation of Serbia and EU regulation, were not exceeded in the analysed samples and hence pose no risk to consumers.

KEY WORDS: budimska sausage; cajna sausage; kulen; PAH; sremska sausage

Elemental composition and health risk of hemp foods

Lj. Torović^{1,2**}, D. Lukić², T. Mrdja¹, N. Kladar¹, and S. Bijelović^{1,2}

¹*Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Novi Sad, Serbia*

²*Institute of Public Health of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia*

Bioaccumulation of harmful toxic elements is the intrinsic signature of the *Cannabis* species. When industrial cannabis (hemp) is used for food products, they have no market value if the elemental contamination is above the permissible level. Elemental composition (23 elements) of 46 hemp foods (20 oils, 9 protein, 12 seeds, 3 sweets, and 2 beverages) was obtained by inductively coupled plasma mass spectrometric (ICP-MS) analysis and further propagated into risk assessment for hemp foods consumers. Regarding non-carcinogenic risk, the hazard quotient (HQ) of each individual element in any of the samples was below the limit of 1 when the adult population was considered. However, in case of older and younger adolescents, the HQ for Hg in 1 seed sample, and additionally for younger ones, for Mn in 1 seed and 1 protein sample, exceeded the limit. The hazard index, a summary metric for all elements in a sample, exceeded 1 for numerous samples: 1 oil, 8 protein, and 6 seed samples in case of adult consumers, an additional 2 seeds for older adolescents, and 1 protein and 5 seeds for younger adolescents. The margin of exposure (MOE) associated with Pb nephrotoxicity was below 10 for the 4 oils and 1 seed sample if consumed by adults, but an additional 1 and 2 seeds for older and younger adolescents, respectively. The carcinogenic risk due to As exposure exceeded the tolerable 1 extra lifetime cancer case per 100,000 persons across the population groups, for 11/13/16 samples, or, when the MOE approach was applied, for 0/2/4 samples. Consumption of hemp foods by children would be even more disputable.

KEY WORDS: hazard index; ICP-MS; Lifetime Cancer Risk; margin of exposure; food safety

*jasna.djinovic@inmes.rs

**ljilja.torovic@mf.uns.ac.rs